

DHIS 2 Consultants Directory

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Summary

A group of nonprofit organizations is launching an online directory of DHIS 2 consultants, tools and templates that would be managed by the DHIS 2 community. This document suggests some of the elements that could be included as well as a possible governance structure and approval processes.

Background

In November 2016, participants at a DHIS 2 conference in Geneva Switzerland recommended a list of twelve actions (see Appendix 1) to increase the effectiveness of DHIS 2 in addressing global health issues. [\[1\]](#) The three top-ranked actions were:

- Provide training material that includes good examples of reports, dashboards and indicators using best practices. The training materials should help users design an effective system that will actually be used, and that can act as templates for implementations.
- Provide a list of qualified DHIS 2 experts and contractors with their specialties and experience to make it easier to find relevant help. The process for listing experts should be transparent and credible, and should highlight regional expertise in the global South to build capacity and promote South-South collaboration.
- Create packages of DHIS 2 forms, programs, data elements, indicators, reports and dashboards that users can copy and adapt for their own purposes rather than creating them from scratch. For example, develop logistics processes, indicators and template configurations for emergency situations so that DHIS 2 can be implemented quickly in emergencies

LogicalOutcomes, which is a nonprofit organization based in Canada, has offered to set up an initial consultant directory that will be shared publicly. This directory will invite consultants to submit descriptions of themselves and their services, and link to tools, templates and use cases that they have worked on. We hope that other organizations will join us in managing the directory, and that it will eventually be led by a broad community group.

Relationship with University of Oslo

The University of Oslo's Health Information Systems Program (UiO) is supportive of this initiative and is willing to link to its resources from the DHIS2.org web site, but will not be a direct sponsor or approval authority. UiO has recommended that an expanded list of people and skills should be open for any

expert to self-register and be neutral in the sense that no organization is controlling who can be there or not. The DHIS 2 web site will continue to host a brief list of experts with whom UiO has experience.

Elements of the resource directory

The proposed directory will contain several linked resources that are aimed at increasing the effectiveness of DHIS 2 implementations.

1. Consultants and skills

This would be a directory of DHIS 2 consultants who are available for collaboration and/or contracting. Consultants would submit themselves for inclusion in the list through a survey form. The directory should be searchable and filtered by terms like language, skills, availability, location, organization, and network affiliation (e.g., HISP East Africa). The entries would have a brief 'About me' section to highlight interests and experience, but would not be onerously long. For example, the entries would include LinkedIn or ORCID profiles rather than requesting resumes.

The directory would be accompanied by a description of the various skills sets that are necessary for effective DHIS 2 implementations.

Each consultant would have to submit at least one tool or template or use case or user story (with permission from the client) in order to be published on the list. This will build the directory of tools and use cases, and it will also demonstrate the capability of the consultants.

2. Tools and templates

This would be a directory of DHIS 2 tools, articles, apps and templates. These might include guidance documents for implementations; API code and documentation; apps that are not mature enough to be added to the DHIS 2 app store; samples of business cases, budget and project planning templates; validated indicators that can be imported into DHIS 2 instances; and articles on best practices. See the list of recommended actions in appendix 1 for more ideas.

Each tool would be linked to associated consultants and use cases so that users could track who worked on what as a way to identify expertise in specific areas.

3. Use cases and user stories

A directory of DHIS 2 implementations that contain a range of documented use cases or user stories, from massive multi-national and multi-sectoral projects to small NGO pilots. The use cases should be searchable and filtered by terms like size, topic, sector, country, organization and network affiliation, and software integrations (e.g., OpenMRS, CommCare, KoboToolbox, Excel). The descriptions should be

useful for many purposes, including RFP and proposal development and identification of potential collaborators and tools.

Some use cases may be anonymized to protect client privacy, but all of them should be published with the permission of the organization involved.

4. FAQs and policies

The resource list would include Frequently Asked Questions that would address selection and quality criteria, the review process, governance, privacy policy, disclaimers and terms and conditions. The list would have clear guidelines on intellectual property (i.e., open access principles and the necessity of permission from the owner of IP), and a statement that the site does not guarantee that the tools work.

Submission and approval process

1. Individuals and organizations would be invited to self-register on the site using standard templates and post information about themselves, their skills, availability and contact information, tools and templates that they are willing to share with the community, and/or descriptions of their past projects and use cases (with client permission).
2. The submissions would be reviewed for clarity and completeness according to a publicly posted quality checklist. The reviewer might be a paid administrative support person or a volunteer peer reviewer; this would have to be clarified. Depending on resources, the reviewer may be able to help submitters improve their postings.
3. If the submission passed the quality checks, it would be made public on the site. If it was turned down, there would be an appeal process to ensure the fair application of the quality screening.
4. Postings would be updated every year to ensure that they are kept up to date or archived, as appropriate. For example, some tools will become obsolete with new versions of DHIS 2, and some experts may become unavailable for collaboration.

Governance structure

The administrative, review and development work may be funded and managed by a single organization, but with guidance provided by a steering committee. To maximize accessibility and keep expenses down, the work of the committee should be carried out online using distance collaboration tools, and should not require physical meetings.

We propose a community-based steering committee comprised of representatives from a variety of organizations working in the DHIS 2 community. The steering committee would be comprised of volunteers from these organizations, and would review the management of the portal, its content, and its use on a quarterly basis. The steering committee would convene on a quarterly basis to address policy issues and review suggestions and complaints from users.

Members of the committee should reflect multiple stakeholders, with some minimum proportion representing HISP nodes in the Global South, and voting membership should not be dominated by any one organization. The steering committee should aim to make decisions by consensus rather than on a voting basis.

Next steps

The consultant directory should be launched in the first half of 2017 and then updated regularly. The main tasks are:

Milestone	Description	Date
Initial working group	Create an initial working group to develop the directory. Invite additional participants from the HISP network, independent DHIS 2 experts and organizations providing DHIS 2 services via announcements in the DHIS 2 mailing lists for users and devs and a message to the LinkedIn DHIS 2 experts group.	Mar 2017
Governance model	Clarify a governance model and mobilize volunteer resources to provide direction and define policies for the resource directory. Initially, keep it simple so that we can get the directory launched as quickly as possible.	May 2017
Admin resources	Identify a sustainable funding model to support the directory. It is likely that it will require some ongoing administrative support that would be difficult to obtain from volunteers, and it would be wise to have more than one funding source. Consider for example the HISP Partnership Organization (HPO), HISP East Africa and the West African Health Organization (WAHO). Initially, begin with volunteer resources from participating groups and individuals. Define feasible ongoing funding model for a minimum level of support by December 2017.	Initial resources committed: Mar 2017 Ongoing resources committed: Dec 2017
Process and workflow	Design a process, templates and work flow for submissions, review, approval, appeals, maintenance and archiving.	May 2017

Communication	Communicate to potential submitters and users via listservs, user groups, etc. to invite comments as well as submissions of experts, tools and use cases. This should be an ongoing stakeholder communication process to ensure that the process remains responsive and transparent.	Mar 2017
Working prototype	Develop working prototype and input content from submitters and existing lists if they exist. For example, ask UiO for permission to use the resource material developed by Metrics for Management.	May 2017
Launch	Launch publicly in beta and then keep improving.	Jun 2017
Future development (if funding is available)	Define business and functional requirements for the resource directory, preferably using rapid prototyping with key users (e.g., see https://sites.google.com/view/dhis2consultants), addressing country needs as inferred from TOR requests to UiO over the past two years, the road maps from countries involved in the Praia meeting for West and Central Africa, and the lessons learned from case studies in Ghana and elsewhere. See appendix 2 for some context and suggestions.	Dec 2017

Appendices

1. Action List from Geneva DHIS 2 Conference

These actions were identified by participants throughout the 5 days of the DHIS 2 Executive Introduction and Conference in Geneva. Participants rated the actions between November 18 (the final day of the event) and November 24 2016. We received 34 responses. Possible scores were 'Not a priority' (default response, rated 0), 'Good idea' (rated 1), 'High priority' (rated 2) and 'I may have resources' (rated 3, though the priority order was the same when these items were rated 2). Actions are listed from highest to lowest score. The table below shows the total score of the ratings for each action. [Excerpted from the conference report.]

Topic	Actions	Score
Training	Provide training material that includes good examples of reports, dashboards and indicators using best practices. The training materials should help users design an effective system that will actually be used, and that can act as templates for implementations.	51
Qualified experts	Provide a list of qualified DHIS 2 experts and contractors with their specialties and experience to make it easier to find relevant help. The process for listing experts should be transparent and credible, and should highlight regional expertise in the global South to build capacity and promote South-South collaboration.	51
Templates - DHIS 2 packages	Create packages of DHIS 2 forms, programs, data elements, indicators, reports and dashboards that users can copy and adapt for their own purposes rather than creating them from scratch. For example, develop logistics processes, indicators and template configurations for emergency situations so that DHIS 2 can be implemented quickly in emergencies	48
Training	Provide regional level support to countries through training hubs, technical assistance and online training courses.	47
Templates - Indicators	Develop a consolidated registry of useful indicators and data elements that can be endorsed by major donors, countries and NGOs and exported into DHIS 2. The indicators should follow metadata standards.	43
Requirements definition	Create a transparent requirements definition and priority process for DHIS2, clarifying how users can provide input to the roadmap.	39
IDSR	Increase the functionality and effectiveness of DHIS2 in integrated disease surveillance and response, from initial outbreak to notification and response, to ensure that the right information reaches the right decision-makers at all levels of the system.	38

Use cases	Compile inventory of use cases in various applications, including diseases (HIV, TB and Malaria) civil registration, linkages to multiple health and administrative systems (e.g., vaccination records), results-based funding, etc., so that users can find out what is available. This might include an annotated bibliography of papers and academic research that has been done in DHIS 2.	37
Training	Post case studies and group work from past academies and workshops to make them easy for people to find. Make all exercises and group work available to all country users for scale-up of training, grouped by diseases and audiences (e.g. Central, District, Health Facility) and allow countries to translate and localize them.	37
Templates - Indicators	Develop a recommended collection of indicators to assess the effectiveness of the health information system, e.g., number of users, program efficiency, maturity of the health system, cost effectiveness against standard health metrics, etc. that can be imported into a DHIS 2 implementation.	34
Templates - Planning	Develop a repository of templates, sample documents etc for the wider project/programme management activities required for a DHIS2 implementation. They might include project plan, business case/budget, RFI, RFP, risk/issue log, system architecture diagrams, requirements specifications, comms plan, change control, etc.	32
Templates - Costing	Create benchmarks of costs per facility in different situations, including things like connectivity, devices, support, for a realistic implementation of DHIS 2. Include realistic estimates of financial savings (e.g., reduction in paperwork) that would offset the cost.	30

2. Notes from discussion on the development of an expanded experts list

The following notes are excerpted from a summary of a small group discussion at the DHIS 2 Executive Introduction in Geneva on November 16, 2016. The group comprised a mix of academics, NGOs, technical experts and international agency representatives, and the notes were taken by Cyril Pervilhac.

- Participants highlight the urgent need to respond to many varied country Training Academy requests at country level to implement and scale-up DHIS2. This will increase in 2017 and beyond with the geographical and funding scale-up (e.g. current efforts with partners in West and Central Africa with a need for French speaking expertise), and for the expertise to respond to Requests for Proposals (RfPs)
- At present, one of the main bottlenecks for the countries is the very limited roster of expertise available in the Africa region, less than 20 (as per <https://www.dhis2.org/expert-community>) and strongly biased towards S. and E. Africa, and English-speaking countries
- Academies have not contributed so far to building up a sustainable South-South and much needed network of expertise. The discrepancy between the hundreds of experts trained through the Academics and their experiences gained over the years in the countries contrast with the present very limited expertise available through the official web site.
- Organisations that are attempting to offer their services in DHIS2 in a sub-region to other countries have no platform or procedures available to develop or offer their H.R. skills (e.g. AFENET Nigeria available for English speaking countries, www.afenet.net)
- Countries need to define carefully the exact type of expertise needed for what, when in order to increase the chance of finding the right skilled expert they are looking for.
- For DHIS2 implementation, some of the key skills and competencies (i.e. I.C.T. with hardware and software issues vs softer skills such as planning, capacity-building, use of data) for various activities or posts in-country need to well listed at central level (ex. for DHIS2 specific with the recent competency and skills for the 4 core team members (i.e. IT Engineer, Database Manager, Data Manager, and Public Health Specialist).
- Participants acknowledged the risks of having an open roster of consultants which are well known far beyond DHIS2: hijacking names of consultants for large biddings, difficulty of checking the quality of consultants and delivering quality products.

[1] DHIS 2 Executive Introduction and Conference, Geneva, November 2016. See the conference report at https://docs.google.com/document/d/12e58GuyWUJ15kLxIAi3ED2Rc_3G987axyZOUeC8NC1I .

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